

Journal: <https://ifsmrc.org/index.php/aijrm>**HISTORY OF UZBEKISTAN SUFI MARTIAL ART AND ITS DESCENDANTS****Kambarov Nodirjon Sattarovich,**University of Business and Science. Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor. Uzbekistan. Gmail: nodirjonkambarov2@gmail.com

Abstract: This article describes the history, types and descendants of the national Uzbek and Amir Temur martial art, "Sufi martial art". Through this, the necessity, factors, solutions of educating young people as well-rounded individuals in national martial arts, as well as the founding generations, that is, the masters of "Sufi martial art", are expressed and their importance is considered. The teachings and history of "Sufi martial art" are discussed. Its main structural factors and parts are described. The criteria for forming a healthy lifestyle in Uzbekistan, developing students' interest in the "Sufi martial arts" were analyzed and compared with the criteria, and recommendations were made.

Keywords: "Sufi martial arts", Zormergan, Hsinbay, Chakmon battle, "Sufi martial arts", harmonious personality, upbringing, behavior, behavior, healthy lifestyle, national education, universal human values.

ИСТОРИЯ УЗБЕКИСКОГО СУФИЙСКОГО БОЕВОГО ИСКУССТВА И ЕГО ПОТОМКОВ**Камбаров Нодиржон Саттарович,**Университет бизнеса и науки. Доктор философии в области педагогических наук (кандидат наук), доцент. Узбекистан. Gmail: nodirjonkambarov2@gmail.com

Аннотация: В данной статье описывается история, виды и потомки национального узбекского и амирского темурского боевого искусства «суфийское боевое искусство». В связи с этим рассматриваются необходимость, факторы, решения в области воспитания молодежи как всесторонне развитых личностей в национальных боевых искусствах, а также поколения-основатели, то есть мастера «Суфийского боевого искусства», и их значение. Обсуждаются учения и история «Суфийского боевого искусства». Описываются его основные структурные факторы и составляющие. Были проанализированы и сопоставлены с критериями критерии формирования здорового образа жизни в Узбекистане, развития интереса учащихся к «суфийским боевым искусствам», и даны рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: «Суфийские боевые искусства», «Зормерган», «Хсинбай», «Битва Чакмон», гармоничная личность, воспитание, поведение, здоровый образ жизни, национальное образование, универсальные человеческие ценности.

O'ZBEK SO'FIY JANG SAN'ATI VA AVLODLARI TARIXI**Kambarov Nodirjon Sattarovich,**University of Business and Science. Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent. Uzbekiston. Gmail: nodirjonkambarov2@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada milliy o'zbek va Amir Temyr jang san'ati bo'lmish "So'fiy jang san'ati" tarixi, turlari va avlodlari haqida bayon qilingan. Bu orqali milliy yakkakurashlari yoshlarni barkamol shaxs etib tarbiyalashning zarurati, omillari, yechimlari

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hamda “So‘fiy jang san‘ati” asoschi avlodlari yani ustalari to‘g‘risida fikrlar bildirilgan va muhimligi nazarda tutilgan. “So‘fiy jang san‘ati” ta‘limotlari va tarixi muhokama qilinadi. Uning asosiy tarkibiy omillari va qismlari tavsiflanadi. O‘zbekistonda sog‘lom turmush tarzi shakllantirish, o‘quvchi-yoshlarni “So‘fiy jang san‘ati” ga bo‘lgan qiziqishlari rivojlantirish mezonlari tahlili qilindi va mezonlar bilan solishtirildi hamda tavsiyalar berildi.

Kalit so‘zlar: “So‘fiy jang san‘ati”, Zo‘rmergan, Xsinbay, Chakmon jangi, “So‘fiy jangovar olishuvi”, barkamol shaxs, tarbiyalash, xulq, xatti-xarakat, sog‘lom turmush tarzi, milliy tarbiya, umuminsoniy qadriyatlar.

Introduction

One of the important tasks of this era is to educate our youth to be well-educated, capable, and physically, spiritually, aesthetically, and morally mature. We, teachers and trainers, and the state should create ample opportunities and conditions for the free development of young people, their knowledge and understanding of our history, values, and the history, types, and generations of the Uzbek martial art, the “Sufi martial art”. Indeed, such important work is being carried out today regarding a healthy lifestyle.

The history of the national martial art, the “Sufi martial art” and its descendants is described.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS:

In order to educate a person as a well-rounded person in all respects, to develop their interest in education, the martial art of Amir Temur, the “Sufi Art of War”, the history of Sufi warriors and the descendants of this martial art are described. Leading scientists in our country have conducted their research in this regard. These studies are mainly aimed at studying the needs based on national education and values, and many scientists such as R. Abdurasulov, S. Kushkarov, B. Muminov, K. Yusupov, P. Usmanov, N. Azizov, N. Kambarov have conducted research. Articles have been published and dissertations have been written on these studies.

RESULTS, ANALYSES AND VIEWS

Sufi martial arts are something that teaches people to fight not with each other, but with themselves.

Sheikh Ibrahim Adham

"Sufi martial arts" is a way in which a person, throughout his life, strives to strengthen his body, strengthen his spirit, develop aesthetically and morally, and discover new facets of his abilities and possibilities. At the same time, strengthening the fighting style and strategy, realizing the harmony between the universe and man - being, can solve the problem of consciously changing his lifestyle in a person. As a result of such actions, various methods and schools have emerged, partly from the nature of man himself, and partly from the representatives of Eastern martial arts.

The “Sufi martial arts” teaches people not only the art of striking, but also the art of self-defense, strengthening the body and spirit. At the same time, it creates the opportunity for a person to consciously change his lifestyle, realizing the harmony between the world and man, strengthening combat styles and techniques. The basis of such aspirations is partly the nature of man himself, and partly the traditions of the methods and schools founded by martial arts masters [6].

Karate, aikido, muay thai, kurash, judo, taekwondo, as well as the “Sufi martial arts” that are developing in Uzbekistan, also play an important role in educating young people as well-rounded individuals. One of the top priorities is to educate our youth as well-rounded individuals through Uzbek national values, in which our national art forms, folk games, traditions, and at the same time the national “Sufi martial arts” also play an important role.

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The national "Sufi martial arts" not only teaches martial arts, but also educates a person to be physically strong, spiritually alert, with high morals, aesthetically and spiritually. The national "Sufi martial arts" is created in accordance with our values, unique to us and our ancestors, and reflects the spirit, culture and history of our ancestors. The methods and terms of our national martial arts are also named in the Uzbek language.

During the reign of the great commander and statesman Amir Temur, our national martial arts developed and were enriched with new methods. One of these martial arts is the Sufi martial art of "Zormergan".

The Sufi warriors, the Turanian Tigers, were the most selected soldiers of Amir Temur, who had the title of "Thousand Soldiers". They were masters of the "Sufi martial art", who had perfect technical and tactical training. "Sufi martial art", one of our ancient martial arts, remains one of the rich heritages of our people, but one of the types that is being somewhat forgotten. This martial art is preserved in the works of our writers and scientists.

Uzbek Sufi martial arts are a perfect fighting method based on perfection, and its main views are inextricably linked to Sufism (philosophical knowledge). It is said in this martial art that without being a Sufi (sage), it is impossible to enter this martial art and reach its point of perfection. In it, Sufi martial arts are not intended only for fighting. In essence, they serve only to achieve perfection. When we say fighting, we mean developing the methodology of negative energy in the body. Because if the level of negative energy in the body is not proportional to the level of positive energy, a person cannot be perfect.

The Uzbek "Sufi martial arts" has been preserved mainly among the population of the Uyghur Autonomous Region, Inner Mongolia, Ningxia, and Tansu regions, which are now part of China, and it has brought great nourishment and inexhaustible wealth of information to the current Wushu, Xin-i, and Shaolin schools. Even now, the martial arts system practiced by the Muslim population of China is called "Muslim Wushu" or "Sufi martial arts."

One of the Sufi martial arts that has been kept in strict secrecy until now is Xinbai (Hasanbai), unfortunately, there is very little information about it.

There are several systems of martial arts of the descendants of the oppressors, and their names are also found in a way that is characteristic of our mentality. Methods of the Uzbek "Sufi Martial Arts" system: "Darvesh" method, "Hard static" methods, "Kaldirgoch" method, "Soft soft" methods, "Dance" method, "Tutqanaq" method, "Tool-weapon" method, "Rope battle" method, ("Rumol battle" method), "Shapaloq" method, "Clinging" method, "Kurash-fist" method, "Chakmon battle" method, "Animal" methods, "Besht fist" method, "Kul-elbow" method, "Loy tepar" method, "Sufi old man" method, "Kochqor battle" method, "Etak-eng qoqqish" method.

This martial art has now become a family secret in our country and in the Central Asian region. Examples of these include the "Qarab tep" martial art in the Farij district, the "Uzib ol" martial art system in the Surkhandarya region, and the "Kulu jangi", "Sufi martial art", "Sufi martial arts", "Shakli Daryo jangi", and "Shakli Deniz jangi" systems developed by the Zormergan descendants in the Jizzakh region.

Our Sufi martial arts play an important role in educating a person striving for perfection. The main idea is to educate a person to be physically and mentally healthy, aesthetically and spiritually beautiful. I consider it important to develop Sufi martial arts and use it in educating the younger generation, all people. Through this, we will carry out work such as studying and understanding our national values, history, educating the younger generation as patriots, forming in them concepts of national pride, studying true Islamic teachings, advanced modern knowledge, and thereby creating strong spiritual immunity to protect against various trends.

According to the teachings of this martial art, a person engaged in "Sufi warfare" will not become a soulless machine or a worm with bloodshot eyes in battle. A Sufi warrior never loses his

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identity. He performs his duty as a perfect human being. He does not feel the need for mental treatment, going crazy. In Sufi martial arts, a person is also trained in these spiritual processes. In fact, what is called spiritual, in addition to the spiritual energy system, there is also a higher energy system. As a result of research, we saw that almost no source writes about this.

Cellular movement is diversified. A harmonious movement system is created, similar to the movement of the swallow, which is the symbol of Sufi martial arts. The more active the movement of human cells, the stronger their energy system. If the opposite happens, this person will fall into a state of lethargy, drowsiness, sluggishness, inactivity, indifference and lack of understanding. Sufi martial arts, while activating the movement of cells through breathing, infuses it with the power of the higher spirit. This is the attainment of the level of perfection. This is the level of merging, walking, and absorption with the higher consciousness [1].

The Sufi warrior is taught to be healthy and have good morals. This is precisely the goal of Sufi martial arts. It is clear from this that the pedagogical teachings of Sufi martial arts are aimed at educating young people as well-rounded individuals and are of great importance [4].

We need to learn about the history and ancestors (masters) of "Sufi martial arts".

BORTA BATYR
(*XII - XIII centuries*)

Borta Batyr was born in the city of Panjikent. He was engaged in Sufi martial arts and medicine. He left behind historical manuscripts on Sufi martial arts and medicine. Borta Batyr, having perfect knowledge of shamanism and Buddhism, was engaged in divine science and Sufism. He gave military and spiritual knowledge to the kings and famous commanders of that time and became famous as an advisor. It is said in the legends that dervishism was his profession. He perfectly knew medicine and treated people. As a miraculous person, he was considered the owner of secret knowledge. Borta Batyr is the basis of the "Natharholi" gymnastics system.

BOYCHA BATYR
(*13th - 14th centuries*)

He served as the commander-in-chief of Uzbek Khan in the Turanian lands, in the territory of the Golden Horde from Kiev to Moscow and Astrakhan. The Mamluks (Mamoliks) knew the art of war perfectly and applied it in practice. Historical sources mention that he was a person who reached the rank of governor. Boycha Batyr did a lot of work in the field of physical and spiritual education. He trained many students in the art of war [5].

SAPARBIY

(*13th - 14th centuries*)) *Son of Borta Batyr*

He was the commander-in-chief of the kingdoms in the Turanian lands. He formed special "lifeguards" soldiers and taught them martial arts. He trained warriors. Saparbiy also reached the rank of a saint. He is also famous for having studied the sciences of divine medicine and being able to provide medical care to soldiers wounded in battles. He was also a commander, martial arts master, and physician who was engaged in religious, physical, and spiritual

teachings.

KHALIQL (ZORMERGAN)

(14 th century) Son of Borta Batyr

Raised from a simple shepherd to the rank of batyr (warrior) and played a key role in training the tsar's special guard group. The founder of the martial art of Zormergan (Sufi war). Developed unarmed fighting methods and a system. Like his fathers, he had his own methods of treatment and developed methods of treatment with medicinal herbs. The successor of Zormergan's historical manuscripts. In particular, Zormergan (Sufi war) not only laid the foundation for the martial art, but also brought it to the level of art.

ZORMERGAN

(13 th - 14th centuries) sons of Khaliql

He served the kingdoms of Turan as a commander and bodyguard. Zormergan, founded by his father, further developed the art of martial arts and perfected the methods of working with weapons. Based on the practices of his ancestors, he developed Sufi medicine and enriched and continued the manuscripts. His practices are still used today. He was also a master of the Zormergan art of martial arts.

DAVUD BATYR

(15 th-16th centuries) Sons of Zormergan

Remaining faithful to the traditions of his ancestors, he raised Sufi medicine and martial arts to a higher level and enriched them with methods. He made a great contribution to passing on this art to future generations. Zormergan left behind rare manuscripts on martial arts and medicine.

KOYBOGOR

(15th-16th centuries) Sons of Davud Batyr

He founded the wrestling systems of kurash and stone lifting in a unique style and taught them to his ten sons and disciples. He spread his fame by participating in festivals and celebrations in the territories of present-day Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Afghanistan and Uzbekistan.

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MUHAMMAD MUSO
(17th-18th centuries)

During the reign of the Emirate of Bukhara, he was engaged in religious teachings and prayer. He was a physician and scholar who deeply studied the medicine of the saints. He was a religious leader who had a perfect knowledge of the Holy Quran and trained many disciples.

KOCHQOR MULLA-TABIB
(17th-19th centuries) Sons of Muhammad Musa

A healer who established a system of treatment with prayer and medicinal herbs. He attained the rank of saint. Together with his brothers, he developed the martial art of “One Punch Blow” and became known in history as the “Besht Mush” battle. He was a master of this martial art. The “Besht Mush” battle was widely used in practice.

There is information in the manuscripts that Kochqor Mulla-Taibib treated very serious diseases. Many “Kochqor Ota” shrines in Central Asia are associated with the name of Kochqor Mulla-Taibib.

BABAYOR AMIN
(19th-20th centuries)

Babayor Amin ruled the emirate for twenty years, and for eighteen years during the reign of Tsar Nicholas. Sources say that he was a sharp politician, orator, and physician. The territories of the present-day Sughd region of Tajikistan, and the Jizzakh, Syrdarya, and Tashkent regions of Uzbekistan belonged to this emirate.

NURBOY OTA

(19th-20th centuries) Son of the Kochqor mullah-tabib

He was famous for his profession of traumatology. Master of kopkari competitions. He was engaged in wrestling, wrestling using the methods of the “Sufi art of war”. He has transmitted the “Sufi art of war” and medicine to us orally. According to sources, Khizr met him and talked about future generations and their practices. Nurboy ota was also a follower, master, and physician of the “Sufi art of war”.

BUVAIDA (KHOLBUVI) MOMO

(19th-20th centuries)

The successor of the martial art of Zormergan, he passed down the history of the “Sufi martial art” dynasty to us. Zormergan systematized, developed and applied the “Chakmon martial art” method of the “Sufi martial art”. The slogan is the basis for the method of fighting with the chakmon, which is an ancient Uzbek national costume. He secretly passed down the system of Sokin gymnastics to generations. Master of the “Chakmon martial art” method.

ZULAYHO MOMO

(20th century) Daughters of Nurboy

She

Zulayho Momo is a master of secret and public incantations. From the powerful "Sufi martial arts" dynasty. was one of the successors of this martial arts, she unified and further clarified the system of abstract movements. She further developed the swallow movements.

MUSTAN OTA

Son of Nurboy ota

Mustan ota is also from the Zormergan “Sufi Art of War” dynasty. He developed the “Sufi Art of War” and founded its “Poisonous Strike” method. This method is aimed at striking the necessary points and directing spiritual energy. A bookworm. He has read many books. Mustan ota is a Sufi warrior, healer, and enlightener.

SUFIY DOCTOR NURSAFARDI

Son of Nurboy ota

Continuing the traditions of his ancestors and based on divine inspiration, he brought Sufi martial arts and medicine into a perfect system and began to widely apply it in practice. He opened several centers in this regard and created works on the “Sufi martial arts”. Sufi doctor Nursafardiy put the Sumergan martial arts into a single mold and applied it in practice. He is a master, martial artist and doctor who has collected all the methods of the “Sufi martial arts” and continues the traditions of the teacher and student. Based on the legacy left by his ancestors, the saint founded the philosophy of

“Nursafardiya”.

ULUGZOR SUFI

Son of Nursafardi

Ulugzor Sufi also practiced the martial arts of Zo'mergan, wrote a number of related literature, and managed to open the martial arts centers "Qatron" and "Zormergan". Now, engaged in perfect systems, he has achieved the title of "Sufi martial arts successor, master, and physician". Ulugzor Sufi is the successor of the heritage of his ancestors.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that our Sufi warriors are the Turanian tigers who played an important role in the formation of the great Turanian state.

We have considered the history of our national martial arts and their founders, the technical-tactical, philosophical, and pedagogical education of young people in the Sufi martial arts above. Based on these ideas, we got acquainted with our Sufi warriors and their feats. We can see the positive pedagogical results of studying and educating the individual personalities of our martial artists, educating them as well-rounded individuals in each exercise of the “Sufi martial arts”, and using various forms and methods. We will achieve their development as physically, morally, aesthetically, and spiritually strong young martial artists through Eastern martial arts.

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